

susceptible or susceptible to new BPH populations, except the Minh hai population. The resistance of ASD7 (*bph* 2) broke down in Mekong Delta, indicating that biotype 2 BPH had developed a new, distinct biotype. Rathu Heenati (*Bph* 3) was particularly resistant to Angiang, Haugiang, and Minh hai populations, but moderately susceptible to those of Tiengiang and Cuulong. PTB33 (digenic gene) was still resistant to all populations. Babawee (*bph* 4) was moderately susceptible to the new BPH biotype.

BPH virulence in Mekong Delta is becoming higher than that of biotype 2 because of natural adaptive selections. Reactions of different populations in various areas were not similar; therefore they were geographically biotypes of BPH somewhere in Mekong Delta. □

Yield losses due to stalk-eyed fly (SEF) in Nigeria

R. C. Joshi, *International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Ibadan, Nigeria (present address: 192 Sun Antonio. Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines); C. J. Angcla, Entomology Department, University of the Philippines at Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines; and M. N. Ukwungwu, National Cereals Research Institute, Badeggi, Nigeria*

Heavy infestation (deadheart) of SEF *Diopsis longicornis* Macquart is observed every year at the IITA experimental farm in Nigeria. This infestation precedes the off-season when SEF adults emerge from weeds to colonize early transplanted rice.

We studied yield losses caused by SEF in early 1989 wet season (WS) in four irrigated lowland rices: FARO 8 (MAS), ITA306, TN1, and IR20. Grain yields from single hills were compared.

SEF damage was at its peak 2 wk after transplanting. Infested and healthy hills were randomly selected, tagged, SEF damage (% per hill) assessed, and grain yields (at maturity) recorded. Hills were monitored weekly for pests other than SEF, but none attained threshold level.

Damaged tillers from each hill were categorized (see table). Hills with an equal number of productive tillers were selected from both infested and healthy

Effect of SEF damage on grain yields of 4 lowland irrigated rices.^a IITA, Nigeria, 1989 wet season.

Rice variety	Total hills (no.)	Grain yield (g/hill, $\bar{X} \pm$ SD)					Yield loss/hill (g)
		Infested tillers				Healthy hill	
		1–20%	21–40%	≥41	<60%		
FARO 8 (MAS)	56	30.2 ± 16.7 (57)	23.3 ± 13.0 (43)	– (0)	27.0 ± 14.9	35.8 ± 19.0	8.8
ITA306	276	17.1 ± 7.8 (54)	14.9 ± 11.0 (41)	22.0 ± 10.0 (5)	18.0 ± 9.6	18.1 ± 10.0	0.1
TN1	76	17.7 ± 9.0 (68)	11.6 ± 9.0 (29)	10.0 ± 0.0 (3)	13.1 ± 6.0	16.0 ± 7.0	2.9
IR20	124	18.3 ± 12.5 (44)	12.0 ± 8.8 (50)	6.7 ± 3.6 (6)	12.3 ± 8.3	21.6 ± 7.0	9.3

^aValues in parentheses indicate hills infested (%) in that category.

hills to minimize differences in yield potential.

The largest percentage of hills showed 1–20% damage (except those of IR20). Yield losses to SEF varied among varieties and damage varied within categories (except in ITA306).

Grain weight declined with increased SEF damage in all rice varieties except ITA306 (see table). This confirmed our field observation that SEF-damaged ITA306 plants recover from infestation; we could not detect yield losses at this damage level. □

Stress tolerance

A simple technique for mass screening of rice germplasm tolerant of photo-oxidation

Jiao Demao and Gu Xinying, *Institute of Agrobiological Genetics and Physiology, Jiangsu Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Nanjing 210014, China*

Photo-oxidation of chlorophyll is a physiological effect on rice under stress

conditions. We developed a simple technique to screen rice germplasm tolerant of photo-oxidation.

Eight mature rice leaves/plant were detached at different growth stages and submerged in a white tray filled with water containing 10–30 ppm CO₂ and 0.5–0.6% O₂ under sunlight at 30–35 °C for 5–7 d. A transparent glass bar covered the leaves to prevent floating.

Leaf color was graded at the end of treatment on a scale of 1–5 (see table). Photo-oxidation-tolerant varieties were

Grades^a of leaf color in various varieties at heading stage.

Varieties ^b				
Grade 1	Grade 2	Grade 3	Grade 4	Grade 5
Nan geng 35 (J)	BR 1083-4 1-2-4-2- 1 (I)	Nan nong da 4008 (I)	Jia nong xian yu 23 (I)	Milyang 23 (I)
02428 (J)	Hualienyu 124 (J)	3037 (I)	Taiyin1 (I)	IB29B (I)
729 (J)	Tngy 1 (J)	Pusa 33 (I)	Yanxuan 156 (I)	Nj 57161 (I)
020 (J)	Tian rui 408 (I)	C662083 (I)	Shan you 63 (I)	NJ 67022 (I)
Yayou 2 (J)	Niu jiaonuo (J)	Palghar 31-1-3 (I)	Nan geng 11A/CS7 (J)	Guicha 02 (I)
		IR44526-47-3-2 (I)	7901-TR16-1-1 (I)	IR58 (I)
		Ge 1868-5-4 (I)	E 164 (I)	Sixizhan (I)
		Ha 361 (I)	Shui tuan 287 (I)	Colombia (I)
		Zong yu 87-1 (I)	IRI346 (I)	Laijing (I)
		Tai nan sen 12 (I)	Della (I)	ITA222 (I)
		Min ke zao 6 (I)	Minyu 4399 (I)	
		CT6417-2-1-1-1p (I)	Zhong yu 4376 (I)	
		Nannong nuo4001 (I)	Yunxia 32 (I)	
		Let 9702 (I)	Nancarp A (I)	
		Sipi 681032 (I)	Bknlr-75091 (I)	
		Xiao jia nuo (I)	Jia nong xian yu 23 (I)	
		IR36 (I)	Min ke zao 1 (I)	
		Nj 701 35 (I)	Ai ma hang (I)	
		Xiang zhong sen 2 (I)	Leah (I)	
		Milyang 23 (I)		

^aGrades (scores) 1 = green, 2 = yellowish tip, 3 = yellowish 1/3, 4 = yellowish 1/2, 5 = yellowish whole leaf. ^bJ = japonica, I = indica.